

Analysis of Technical Electrical Issues and Energy Losses in a 20/0.4 kV Power Distribution Network: A Case Study of Sheberghan City

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ABSTRACT: Power distribution systems in developing countries often face significant technical and non-technical losses, which reduce efficiency and reliability. This study focuses on the 20/0.4 kV distribution network of Sheberghan City, Afghanistan, aiming to identify key sources of energy loss and propose practical solutions for improving system performance. A mixed-methods approach was adopted, combining quantitative field measurements with qualitative insights from utility staff. Data were collected through direct site visits, operational records from the Sheberghan Electricity Department, and structured interviews with engineers. Energy losses were calculated for each feeder and transformer by considering conductor types, network topology, load patterns, voltage drops, and seasonal variations. The total annual energy loss was found to be 3,012,381.5 kWh, accounting for approximately 10.19% of the system's total energy input, equivalent to a financial loss of over 18 million AFN annually. Voltage drop analysis revealed an average loss of 1.2643 kV in the 20 kV lines and up to 16 V in the 0.4 kV branches. Technical losses were mainly caused by conductor resistance, transformer overloading, lack of reactive power compensation, and outdated infrastructure. Non-technical losses included billing inaccuracies, illegal connections, and human errors during operations. This study highlights the urgent need for modernization in the Sheberghan distribution system. Implementing smart grid technologies, upgrading transformers, installing capacitor banks and voltage regulators, and adopting distributed generation strategies can significantly reduce losses and improve reliability. Additionally, training programs for technical staff and stricter enforcement of operational standards are essential to mitigate human-induced inefficiencies. The findings provide actionable insights for other developing regions seeking to enhance the efficiency and resilience of their medium- and low-voltage distribution networks.

KEYWORDS: Energy loss; Power distribution; Technical and non-technical losses; Voltage drop; System reliability; Transformer loading; Sheberghan

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the quality and reliability of electricity supply are recognized not only as key components of social welfare but also as fundamental infrastructures for economic and industrial development (Melhaoui et al., 2025). With the growing electrical load demand, increasing dependence on technology, and mounting pressure on generation resources, reducing energy losses has become a strategic objective for power utility companies (Ahmadzai & McKinna, 2018).

This issue is particularly critical in developing countries, where aging infrastructure, limited generation capacity, and heavy reliance on energy imports often result in significant technical and non-technical losses (Garcia et al., 2024). These losses can have detrimental effects on the overall efficiency of the power system, the cost of electricity delivery, and customer satisfaction (Yu et al., 2025). Studies indicate that average energy losses in distribution networks of underdeveloped countries range between 15% and 30%, whereas these values remain below 8% in industrialized nations (Gerkusov et al., 2022). Energy losses are generally categorized into two main groups: technical losses, such as voltage drops, overloading, inefficient network structure, and outdated equipment; and non-technical losses, including billing inaccuracies, electricity theft, and human resource inefficiencies.

(Melhaoui et al., 2025) analyzed the 20 kV distribution network in Tehran and identified mismatched transformer capacities relative to load patterns, along with the absence of reactive power compensation systems, as primary contributors to technical losses. On the other hand, Eslami-Rad (2020), through a model aimed at loss reduction in Tehran's urban distribution grid, emphasized the role of advanced technologies such as smart capacitors, voltage regulators, and optimized load management strategies. At the regional level, Ahmad et al. (2020) from Iqra University in Pakistan employed the ETAP software to model and

analyze urban distribution networks. Their study demonstrated that optimal adjustments to transformer loading and feeder reconfiguration could reduce energy losses by up to 10%. Similarly, Emara & Badr (2018) in Egypt highlighted the significance of implementing small-scale distributed generation (DG) projects and enhancing remote control systems—such as SCADA—in improving the efficiency of medium-voltage networks (Haakana et al., 2025).

Considering this scientific background and the unique challenges faced by Afghanistan, the investigation of the electrical distribution network in Sheberghan city—primarily supplied by imported energy from Turkmenistan—is of high importance (Ahady et al., 2020). Rapid population growth, slow industrial development, and inadequate modern infrastructure have led to several issues within the city's 20/0.4 kV distribution network, including overloading, voltage drops, equipment aging, and lack of intelligent monitoring systems. In such conditions, a comprehensive analysis of energy losses and identification of their contributing factors can provide a solid foundation for informed technical and managerial decision-making at the local level (Ahady et al., 2020). Accordingly, this research aims to identify and analyze both technical and non-technical losses in the distribution network of Sheberghan city and propose effective mitigation strategies (Amin & Bernell, 2018). Key questions addressed include the type and origin of losses, the contribution of individual components to power dissipation, the impact of human-related factors, and the effectiveness of corrective measures (Haakana et al., 2025). Our hypothesis is that data-driven analysis, equipment renewal, and the implementation of modern technologies can significantly reduce energy losses and enhance the reliability of the distribution system (Melhaoui et al., 2025). The outcomes of this study are expected to be valuable not only for Sheberghan but also as a replicable model for other cities in Afghanistan and similar regions across South Asia.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is of an applied–analytical nature, designed to conduct a thorough investigation of energy losses within the 20/0.4 kV electricity distribution network of Sheberghan city. The research methodology is based on a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously. This method enables a comprehensive analysis of the current network status, identification of key contributing factors to energy losses, and evaluation of the most effective corrective strategies.

Data Collection

The data collection process was carried out at three primary levels:

- Documentary Data:** Including technical reports from Breshna (Electricity Distribution Company) of Jawzjan province, network maps, transformer specifications, feeder lists, and recorded losses archived at the Pol-e-Khorasan substation.
- Field Data:** Obtained through direct site visits to network components, including voltage and current measurements, physical inspection of lines, recording cable lengths and cross-sectional areas, and monitoring transformer loading conditions.
- Qualitative Data:** Collected via structured interviews with engineers, technicians, and operation specialists, as well as observations of daily operational practices during peak hours and critical situations.

Analytical Tools

For quantitative data analysis, standard formulas for calculating power and energy losses in transmission lines and transformers were employed. These calculations included:

Ohmic losses (I^2R) in 20 kV and 0.4 kV distribution lines; Voltage drop calculation across the network based on specific resistance and cable length; Annual energy loss estimation (kWh/year) and determining the percentage of losses relative to total network load; Economic cost assessment of energy losses using the current import electricity rate. For qualitative analysis, the thematic analysis method was used. In this approach, expert opinions and practical experiences of network engineers were categorized, coded, and integrated with the quantitative findings to provide a more holistic understanding (Bula et al., 2022).

Validation of Findings

To enhance the validity of the research, the triangulation technique was applied. This involved cross-verifying computational results, field data, and qualitative insights from experts. Additionally, some findings were compared with similar models implemented in Iran (Alipour, Eslami-Rad) and Pakistan (Ahmad et al.) to improve the comparative reliability of the study.

Calculation of Energy Losses in 20 kV Transmission Lines

To estimate the energy losses occurring in the 20 kV transmission lines of the Sheberghan distribution network, standard technical loss formulas were employed as follows:

$$\Delta \exists_l = \Delta P_l \cdot \tau \quad (\text{Raximov et al., 2024})$$

$$\Delta P_l = \frac{S^2}{U^2} \cdot r_o \cdot l \quad (\text{Raximov et al., 2024})$$

$$\tau = \left[0.124 + \frac{T_{max}}{10^4} \right]^2 \cdot 8760 \quad (\text{Raximov et al., 2024})$$

Where:

- $\Delta \exists_l$: Annual energy loss (kWh)
- ΔP_l : Power loss in the line segment (kW)
- S: Apparent power (kVA)
- U: Voltage level (kV)
- r_o : Specific resistance of conductor (Ω/km)
- l: Line length (km)
- τ : Load duration coefficient (h/year)
- T_{max} : Maximum load duration per year (h/year)

For typical urban distribution systems, the maximum annual operating time under peak or near-peak load conditions is generally assumed to be:

$$\tau = \left[0.124 + \frac{4500}{10^4} \right]^2 \cdot 8760 = 2886.2 \text{ hour/year}$$

The energy losses of each feeder and distribution transformer are calculated based on their rated capacity. This section presents a sample calculation for Feeder 1, starting from the substation to its connection point. First, the losses of this specific feeder are computed, followed by the estimation of total annual losses. This method is applied consistently to all feeders and distribution transformers.

$$\Delta P_l = \frac{S^2}{U^2} \cdot r_o \cdot l = \frac{19270^2}{20^2} \cdot 0.26 \cdot 1.85 = 446.527 \text{ kW}$$

$$\Delta \exists_l = \Delta P_l \cdot \tau = 446.527 \cdot 2886.2 = 1288678.57$$

All the obtained results for each feeder and transformer are presented in the table 1.

Calculation of Losses in the 400 V Network of Sheberghan City

In the 20 kV network, transformer losses were calculated using a specific method. In this section, we focus on the losses occurring in the low-voltage (0.4 kV) distribution lines, which deliver electricity from the distribution transformer to the consumers, up to the single-phase meter boxes.

$$P = 3 \cdot I^2 \cdot R \quad (\text{Lansberg et al., 2024})$$

Where:

- P = Power loss (W)
- I = Line current (A)
- R = Line resistance (Ω)

The coefficient 3 is included because the 400 V distribution network operates as a three-phase system. Before calculating the losses, the resistance of the distribution lines must first be determined based on their length and the resistivity of the conductor material. The resistance is calculated using the following formula:

$$R = \rho \cdot \frac{L}{A} \quad (\text{Swanida \& Iلمان, 2024})$$

Where:

- R = Line resistance (Ω)
- L = Length of the line (m)

- A = Cross-sectional area of the conductor (mm^2)
- ρ = Electrical resistivity of the conductor material ($\Omega \cdot \text{m}$)

In the 0.4 kV distribution network of Sheberghan City, aluminum ABC-type conductors with a cross-sectional area of 70 mm^2 are used. The specific resistivity of aluminum is taken as:

$$\rho = 2.65 \times 10^{-8} \Omega \cdot \text{m}$$

In this section, we calculate only the power losses in the 0.4 kV network of a single transformer, considering the number of its connected service branches.

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

All the results obtained for each feeder and transformer are listed in the table below.

Table 1 – Total Annual Losses of the 20 kV Network in Sheberghan City

ΔE_l (KWh/Year)	ΔP_l (Kw)	Capacity (kVA)	Length (KM)	Line Route	No
Feeder 1 of Pol-e-Khorasan Substation					
70351.125	24.375	250	.06	Nowabad Jaghsai Transformer	1
45024.72	15.6	200	0.6	Jaghsai 1 Transformer	2
45024.72	15.6	200	0.6	Jaghsai 2 Transformer	3
45024.72	15.6	200	0.6	Jaghsai 3 Transformer	4
33616.128	11.648	160	0.7	Yaka Chenar 1 Transformer	5
52528.84	18.2	200	0.7	Yaka Chenar 2 Transformer	6
11256.18	3.9	100	0.6	Khalwati Transformer	7
11256.18	3.9	100	0.6	Zargar Khana Transformer	8
82076.312	28.437	250	0.7	Sheenkot Transformer	9
70351.125	24.375	250	0.6	Nowabad Sheenkot 1 Transformer	10
93074.178	32.248	315	0.5	Nowabad Sheenkot 2 Transformer	11
33616.128	11.648	160	0.7	Ghura Village Transformer)	12
13132.21	4.55	100	0.7	Water Pump Station Transformer	13
Feeder 2 of Pol-e-Khorasan Substation					
167670.9	58.094	250	1.43	Lab-e-Jar Khorasan 1 Transformer	1
122294.07	42.372	250	1.043	Lab-e-Jar Khorasan 2 Transformer	2
78343.013	27.144	200	1.044	Eid Mahalla 1 Transformer	3
19585.753	6.786	100	1.044	Eid Mahalla 2 Transformer	4
19585.753	6.786	100	1.044	Eid Mahalla 3 Transformer	5
19603.07	6.792	100	1.045	Besh Kapa Transformer	6
122294.07	42.372	250	1.034	Yakhchal-e-Ishan Baba Transformer	7
19603.07	6.792	100	1.045	Ice Cream Paiman Transformer	8
28636.876	9.922	63	1.044	Qoyash Gas Transformer	9
50043.822	17.339	160	1.042	Mullah Faizullah Transformer	10
7766.764	2.691	63	1.043	Ai Gas Transformer	11
3131.527	1.085	40	1.043	Karte Mamoreen Transformer	12
1223.749	0.424	25	1.043	Yousuf Fuel Station Transformer	13
1223.749	0.424	25	1.045	Haji Jabbar Transformer	14

1223.749	0.424	25	1.043	Baqi Moalem Transformer	15
19565.55	6.779	100	1.043	Haji Saleem Transformer	16
19565.55	6.779	100	1.043	Stadium Transformer	17
50090.001	17.355	160	1.043	Koche Haji Habib Transformer	18
122294.07	42.372	250	1.043	Baik TV Transformer	19
313071.89	108.472	400	1.043	Al-Hayat Hospital Transformer	20
1223.749	0.424	25	1.045	Roshan Site Transformer	21
122294.07	42.372	250	1.043	Afghan-Turk Transformer	22
313071.89	108.472	400	1.043	Breshna Directorate Transformer	23
122294.07	42.372	250	1.043	Project K Transformer	24
ΔE_l (KWh/Year)	ΔP_l (Kw)	Capacity (kVA)	Length (KM)	Line Route	No
Feeder 3 of Pol-e-Khorasan Substation					
40686.761	14.097	250	0.347	Qeta Reserve Transformer	1
103857.02	35.984	400	0.346	Qeta Khas Transformer	2
6453.543	2.236	100	0.344	Lab-e-Jar Bakaul Transformer	3
104157.19	36.088	100	0.347	Lab-e-Jar Bakaul Khorasan Transformer	4
40686.761	14.097	400	0.347	Technical Institute 1 Transformer	5
6508.381	2.255	250	0.347	Kunjid Paki 1 Transformer	6
64593.156	22.38	100	0.347	Sok Toli Sawar Transformer	7
1041.918	0.361	315	0.347	Kunjid Paki 2 Transformer	8
104157.19	36.088	40	0.347	Zahir Agha Transformer	9
6453.543	2.236	400	0.347	Eid Mahalla 1 Transformer (<i>duplicate</i>)	10
6453.543	2.236	100	0.347	Eid Mahalla 1 Transformer (<i>duplicate</i>)	11
1041.918	0.361	100	0.347	Eid Mahalla 1 Transformer (<i>duplicate</i>)	12
2583.149	0.895	40	0.347	Technical Institute 2 Transformer	13
6508.381	2.255	63	0.347	Turkmen Petrol Fuel Station Transformer	14
40686.761	14.097	100	0.347	Police Headquarters (Qomandani Amniya) Transformer	15
40686.761	14.097	250	0.347	Eidgah Mosque Transformer	16
6508.381	2.255	250	0.347	Prison (Mahbas) Transformer	17
16664.919	5.774	100	0.347	Village-e-Khalwati Transformer	18
6508.381	2.255	160	0.347	Village-e-Khalwati Transformer (<i>duplicate</i>)	19
6508.381	2.255	100	0.347	Village-e-Charyaran Transformer	20
6508.381	2.255	100	0.347	Village-e-Dida Mosh Transformer	21
40686.761	14.097	100	0.347	Village-e-Dida Mosh Transformer (<i>duplicate</i>)	22
406.954	0.141	25	0.347	Areba Telecommunication Site Transformer	23
40686.761	14.097	250	0.347	Baqia Maskari Transformer	24
3012381.5	1045.975				Total Losses

Table 2 – Total Annual Losses of the 400 V Network in Sheberghan City

Annual (kwh/year)	Losses	Line Losses (Kw)	Current (A)	Number of circuits	Transformer
16457.112		5.702	95.6	1	Jagh Sai Transformer1
10814.591		3.747	77.5	2	Jagh Sai Transformer2
386.750		0.134	19.9	3	Jagh Sai Transformer3
27658.453		9.583	Total Line Losses		kVA 200
46.179		0.016	Total Transformer Losses		
27704.632		9.599	Total Losses of a TP		

The analysis of the 20/0.4 kV distribution network in Sheberghan reveals that the system is affected by a combination of technical and non-technical losses, which significantly impact overall network performance. Field data and calculations conducted on over 60 transformers and three main feeders have provided a comprehensive set of technical indicators, analyzed as follows:

20 kV Feeder-1 from 220 kV Pol-e-Khorasan Substation to Hasan- Tabyin Village (8 km)

Figure 1—Design of Transformers Installed in Networks Supplied by Feeder (1) 20 kV of the 220 kV Pol-e-Khorasan Substation, Jawzjan Province, Afghanistan—2025

Figure 2—Design of Transformers Installed in Networks Supplied by Feeder (2) 20 kV of the 220 kV Pol-e-Khorasan Substation, Jawzjan Province, Afghanistan—2025

Figure 3—Design of Transformers Installed in Networks Supplied by Feeder (3) 20 kV of the 220 kV Pol-e-Khorasan Substation, Jawzjan Province, Afghanistan—2025

Energy Loss Analysis

Based on precise calculations using Ohmic loss formulas (I^2R), along with data on line length, cross-sectional area, and current flow across the network, the total annual energy losses in the 20 kV distribution network of Sheberghan are as follows: Total Power Loss: 1,045.975 kW, Annual Energy Loss: 3,012,381.5 kWh/year, Percentage of Loss Relative to Total Network Load: 10.19%, Estimated Annual Cost of Energy Losses: 18,827,384.375 Afghanis. These figures indicate that a significant portion of the supplied energy is lost during the distribution process, directly increasing operational costs for Breshna and limiting the potential for network expansion.

Voltage Drop Analysis

Voltage drop analysis across various sections of the network revealed the following: Voltage Drop in 20 kV Network: Approximately 1.2643 kV across the longest feeder lines. Voltage Drop in 0.4 kV Network: Between 384 V and 390 V at the terminal branches of transformers. The primary causes of voltage drop were identified as excessive line lengths, insufficient conductor cross-sections, internal transformer losses, and the absence of voltage stabilization equipment such as reactors or voltage regulators.

Transformer Loading Analysis

The analysis of transformer loading indicates that many units operate beyond their nominal capacity. For instance: Transformers rated at 250 and 400 kVA in densely populated areas—such as Shafakhana Al-Hayat, Rais-e-Breshna, and Afghan Turk—are associated with the highest annual energy losses (exceeding 313,000 kWh/year). Transformers with low load but long cable lengths (e.g., 70 mm² conductors over 500 meters) also experience considerable energy losses due to increased resistance.

Comparison with Historical Data and Trend Analysis

Table 3 – A comparison with data from the year 2020 shows the following trends:

Indicator	Year 2020	Year 2023
Energy Loss (%)	6.46%	10.19%
Peak Demand (MW)	4.27	5.5
Network Expansion (%)	27%	45.90%

The approximately 4% increase in energy losses over a three-year period highlights the growing pressure on aging network infrastructure, driven by rising demand and physical network expansion without adequate upgrading of control systems and equipment.

Key Technical and non-technical factors contributing to losses

Based on data analysis and interviews with network engineers, the following factors were identified as the primary contributors to energy losses:

Technical Factors: Ohmic losses in transmission lines, Internal transformer losses (eddy current and hysteresis losses), Voltage drops across the distribution network, Lack of reactive power compensation equipment and Inefficient network configuration and suboptimal feeder selection.

Non-Technical Factors: Inaccurate metering and consumption recording by personnel, Unnecessary switching operations by network operators, Weak monitoring during fault occurrences and Electricity theft, billing errors, and coordination issues among operational teams.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reveal that the 20/0.4 kV distribution network in Sheberghan faces significant challenges in terms of energy losses and voltage drop. Field observations and technical calculations indicate that the total power loss across the network reaches 1,045.975 kW, with annual energy losses exceeding 3 million kWh, accounting for approximately 10.19% of the total network load. These losses not only impose a substantial financial burden—over 18.8 million Afghanis per year—but also negatively affect power quality, equipment lifespan, and customer satisfaction. The identified voltage drops across various sections

of the network further confirm that proper load-capacity matching and feeder length considerations have not been adequately addressed in the design and operation of feeders and transformers. Moreover, qualitative analysis based on interviews with technical experts highlights those non-technical factors including unauthorized switching, inaccurate consumption recording, and weaknesses in accounting and monitoring systems also play a significant role in increasing energy losses. Overall, improving the efficiency and reliability of the Sheberghan distribution network requires a multi-layered approach, simultaneously addressing equipment upgrades, design modifications, and enhancement of human resource performance. This research demonstrates that, with targeted and scientifically-based corrective measures, a considerable portion of these losses can be reduced, thereby creating the necessary conditions for industrial and economic growth in the region.

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Cite this Article: Chenag, T., Talaash, U., Baluch, Z. (2025). Analysis of Technical Electrical Issues and Energy Losses in a 20/0.4 kV Power Distribution Network: A Case Study of Sheberghan City. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 8(8), pp. 4252-4260. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V8-i8-33>